

////////////////////////////////////

IDEA-BROKERING WORKSHOP

A RAPID INNOVATION METHOD THROUGH INTERCONNECTING DIFFERENT CONTEXTS

Yukinobu Yokota¹, Fumiko Ichikawa², Aico Shimizu², Hiroshi Tamura^{1, 2}
¹The University of Tokyo, ²Hakuhodo Inc.
yyokota@ischool.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp

ABSTRACT

In today's dynamic corporate environment, organizations and employees are continuously in demand to think out-of-the-box, how existing products or services could improve, or even be targeted other than the existing market. In order to meet this demand, organizations need to come up with effective ways to gain understanding on certain cultures or people, and generate ideas that reflect the technological advantage they hold within. To meet this demand, we designed a workshop called 'idea brokering', where a group of people would go through two concise sessions, one for 'downloading' the insights from ethnographic research, and another, for some inspiration. The paper describes the approach and a case study workshop.

Keywords: idea-brokering, design workshop, human-centered innovation.

INTRODUCTION

For over a decade, even before the rise of the Internet and globalization, established firms have been facing the challenge of meeting disruptive changes, and have often been unsuccessful in overcoming them (Christensen & Overdorf, 2000). In order to conquer such issues, IDEO and other design firms have been providing human-centered innovation processes, and have shown certain progress. On the other hand, to execute such a process, often requires time and investment: some projects could last for months, or in some cases, years. Often this is not something that an organization could deploy as they keep their business

as usual. Methodology on how we could execute human-centered innovation in a concise yet effective manner is highly expected in corporate practice in the field of product development and design.

In this paper, we propose a new design method, which we created for idea generation that could lead to disruptive changes. This paper describes the methodology and a case study, a workshop where participants generated product ideas for the Indian market.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

As a part of our effort, we have been continuously attempting to discover how innovation can be created in practice. In this section, we introduce i.school, where an effort has been made through collaboration between industry and academia. Some of our approaches utilized in this program, became the backbone of this workshop.

I.SCHOOL: A PLACE FOR CREATIVITY AND INNOVATION

i.school is a cross-disciplinary educational program established by the Center of Knowledge Structuring in the University of Tokyo. The purpose of the program is to develop and provide an educational program, where participants learn to be innovative as they go through various social themes and workshops. i.school is also known for its collaborative nature, as an actual program by default receives not only students but people from the industry concerning the theme. i.school has so far worked with other design schools such as Stanford d.school, Toronto Rotman School, KAIST, Royal College of Arts, and Aalto University, and design

firms such as Hakuhold, Ziba, and IDEO, and other experts (i.school, 2011).

Although many consider the term innovation to be somewhat technological, the program describes its effort as ‘human-centered innovation’ to emphasize that participants would not be limited to the technological side of the innovation. As Verganti (2009) coined with the term “meaning innovation” to describe the significance of innovation derived from human senses, behaviors, routines, and values, i.school students learn methods and experience observations and fieldwork on people and societies.

As two of the authors of this paper are faculty members of i.school, this paper describes some of the insights and outcomes of the human-centered innovation workshops in this program.

IDEA-BROKERING: AN IDEA GENERATION METHOD USING ENVIRONMENTAL SCANNING

‘Idea brokering’ is a new method we propose in this paper and was utilized as the basis of the workshop we designed. The term describes an idea generation, which cross-pollinates two types of information, one of which comes from a familiar, ‘internal’ knowledge or expertise, and another from an unfamiliar, in other words, ‘external’ environment.

This concept of combining two old elements to create innovative idea is not new (Young, 2003; Ichikawa, 1977). We have also seen similar methods that support idea generation in fields of industrial design (Noguchi, 1998) and management (Kim & Mauborgne, 2005).

Among these approaches, a method called environmental scanning has particularly been our interest. Environmental scanning has been utilized in understanding environmental changes and their impact on organizations since the 1960s. Various scholars have defined environmental scanning, however, its essence is to systematically collect information that seems directly irrelevant to an institution’s current business and to define threats and opportunities (Aguiler, 1976; Brown & Weiner, 1985, Coates et al., 1985). What is interesting about

this specific approach, is not only that it recognizes the collision of two different elements to fuse innovation, but recognizes the need to understand the external information and to fuse this with a knowledge or expertise that one holds within one’s own environment.

Having environmental scanning as a source of inspiration, we decided to design an idea-brokering workshop, dedicating two sessions for each of these elements: one, called the Download Session, which brings in ‘external’, unfamiliar information, and another, called the Inspiration Session, which reminded participants of familiar, ‘internal’ information.

DOWNLOAD - UNDERSTANDING EXTERNALITIES

In order to create new ideas in a human-centric manner, it is important that any workshop starts by understanding the people and contexts where ideas should take place. In an idea-brokering workshop, the main session starts with what we call Download Session, where personnel who have conducted ethnographic research in a certain cultural context, share insights to provoke ideas to be built on.

However, when workshops are time-intensive, sharing information from a qualitative research with such rich data can become a great challenge. There needs to be careful consideration not only about what is to be shared but about how it is to be shared.

Although the term ethnography literally suggests it takes the form of writing, anthropologists and corporate researchers have been exploring many ways to share their learning outside of their own culture. In the history of anthropology, many scholars addressed using still photography as a means of research and presenting it (Bateson & Mead, 1942; Byers, 1964). In corporate ethnography, ethnographers and design researchers have been recording their experiences and insights in various forms, from text (Dalsgaard, 2008), photographs (Johnsen & Helmersen, 2008), and videos (Faulkner & Zafiroglu, 2010; Cramer et al., 2008).

In particular, technological advance and digitalization of cameras and storage had substantially decreased the cost and the effort of producing media, not to mention the psychological hurdle to go through trial-and-error of actual shooting. Inexpensive digital video cameras enabled many researchers to utilize the video as a way to captivate and directly convey scenes during research. Cramer et al. (2008) have described videos as often being ‘a natural choice for the researchers’ for this very reason.

Although video clips were as means to share the external information, we as organizers chose to use still photographs as a primary means to inform the participants. As Barthes (1964) coined with the word ‘poly-semic’, photography is a media that provides multiple meanings, and the final interpretation can only be fixated with the presence of the viewer (Barthes, 1981). If compared, photographs may not contain as much information as in the video clips, its still yet sufficiently visual nature can be expected to give more time to the audience, and as a consequence, room to have a certain level of engagement regardless of their prior knowledge: participants who have personal experience visiting or living in this external context, these photographs would work as a reminder of what they have seen earlier; for participants who are completely foreign to this information, any element within the photograph could be a trigger to bring new knowledge and thus questioning how some things that have been tacit in one’s own context.

Furthermore, using photographs for the Download Session also had another advantage, as they can be printed. Collier and Collier (1986) used this process of viewing in their visual anthropology, as they printed and repeatedly reorganized to identify the underlying themes and more questions behind them. Through photograph sorting process, we expect participants to be able to construct a story that is relevant and generate a source of inspiration. We decided to provide the photographs we present to participants as if they were a deck of cards, hoping this would provide an even bigger opening for further inspiration.

INSPIRATION - PROVOKE IDEA GENERATION

During Download, participants were encouraged to understand the values and the everyday behaviors of a foreign, external environment. If Download Session is to initialize our lens and allows us to learn externalities, what does its counterpart, Inspiration Session, bring to the workshop?

Whether by living or working, being in a routine under the very same community often put people in a place where they no longer appreciate how a product, service, or a social system work; however, after learning a different way of living from an external perspective, it becomes much more imminent that things that were taken for granted could also be an asset, which could be adapted or utilized to solve problems in other context. The intention of Inspiration Session is precisely that: to enable participants to revisit their knowledge and experience over their own context and provide them with provoke them with potential ‘seeds’ of ideas.

Just like in Download Session, organizers prepared another set of photographic cards, however, this time as a source of inspiration. Although there are many approaches we could have taken, we chose to place photographs of products that are sold in Japanese market, and are well known to any of the participant.

Products, mechanical parts, and tangible items with different textures, have been used as a tool to provoke inspiration by many disciplines. In the design firm IDEO, a shelf called the Tech Box is placed in the office, filled with a collection of materials with different textures and compositions and items with mechanical elements. The Tech Box is used as a source of inspiration for engineers and designers in the company and for clients (Kelly, 2001).

Another example is cultural probes, which a kit consisted of recording items such as disposable cameras, maps, and journals (Gaver et al., 1999). Cultural probes are often used as a way to research users, by distributed the kit to people in different cultural contexts to be prompted by inspiring tasks that provoke inspirational responses from them.

Although tangible and physical items were provided in existing approaches, we decided it would not be applicable for this workshop. Apart from obvious reasons such as the facility space and the cost of purchasing products, these inspiration materials should be ‘internal’, in other words, familiar products that can be found in one’s own environment. Instead of using time to revisit the precise feature of these products, we thought it would be much more valuable if participants spent time discussing their experiences or values they identify in the existence of this product in our society. For the same reason as Download Session, we decided that inspiration materials should also take the form of photographic cards.

For the selection of products to be presented in this session, the organizers set up a team and searched for products in the market with two identified criteria: (1) Applicability. The item has unique (mechanical or technological) features that can be applied to multiple purposes. (2) Outcome of human-centered innovation. The product itself has been developed based on careful observations and research. Once products were selected, cards were prepared so that each contained not only an image of a product, but also a photograph of its usage scene. Further, for all cards, a short description on what the product is and its purpose was placed onto the card.

PROCESS

The case study we introduce here describes how the idea-brokering workshop can be done in practice.

CASE STUDY: INNOVATION WORKSHOP FOR INDIA

On 25 January 2011, we organized a workshop titled the “Innovation Workshop for India” as a part of the i.school program. The workshop was organized as we had the rare opportunity of having business leaders from India participating in the Visionary Leaders for Manufacturing (VLFM) program (VLFM, 2011).

There were altogether 20 people who attended the workshop. Background of participants varied from industrial designers and researchers in the industry,

to engineering students in graduate schools. In addition, there were 25 observers, including members of the VLFM program from India. There were also 10 people in the organizing group, who supported the facilitation of the workshop.

Session ID	Duration (minutes)	Session Activity
1	15	Introduction
2	90	Download
3	60	Inspiration
4	45	Presentation
5	5	General comment

Table 1: The overall agenda of the workshop. In total we spent 3.5 hours on this session.

SESSION 1: INTRODUCTION

As an opening to the workshop, the facilitator briefly described the agenda and basic rules on how to be creative upon participating in the workshop. Participants were divided into four teams, with even mixtures of students and professionals. Each team sat together and was instructed to work together throughout the workshop.

SESSION 2: DOWNLOAD

After the introduction, four so-called ‘lenses’ were introduced from the organizer. In this workshop, the four were: lifestyle, sustainability, literacy, and social networking. Organizers then assigned these four topics to each team as an area which they should identify issues or opportunities, and come up with ideas that could solve them.

After the introduction, two corporate ethnographers who recently conducted ethnographic research in Bangalore, India, shared some of the insights derived from the field. Download took the form of a presentation, using a set of photographs and oral explanation (Figure 1).

Figure 1: A scene from the Download Session

During the presentation, photographs were shown as slides but without any textual information presented. The purpose of this approach was so that workshop participants would be encouraged to explore elements presented in the photographs instead of text guiding them to look at a specific element within each photograph.

Among the photographs presented, 20 were selected as Download Cards and printed, in Japanese standard 2L size, 127mm in width and 178mm in height. Each team received this set of photographs and was encouraged to freely browse them throughout the workshop.

As photographs were presented, participants used sticky notes to write any interesting or intriguing insights that were relevant to the lens that they were assigned to work on. Notes were later shared among the group and placed onto large panels provided to each of the four teams. After going through another round of brainstorming, each team identified issues around the theme.

SESSION 3: INSPIRATION

After the Download Session, the Inspiration Session took place. Here, the task for the participants was to come up with product ideas and usage scenarios, which would solve the issue they had identified earlier during the Download Session. In order to facilitate the process of generating new ideas, organizers distributed another set of cards, called 'Inspiration Cards'. There were a total of 21

Inspiration Cards (Table 2), identical to the size of the Download Cards.

Criteria	Products
Applicability	Portable hand crank radio
	Mobile phone trinket for display cleaning
	Nike+
	Electric kettle
	Mechanical bicycle parking
	Plastic wrap
	Hair dryer
	Unicycle
	Roller
	Roller Shoes
	Kotatsu - heater-attached low table
Human-Centered Innovation	Personal electric carpet
	Portable waterproof television
	Gopan - rice bread cooker
	Microwave fish grill wrap
	Nintendo DS
	Adhesive bandage
	Shunsoku - sneakers optimized for running tracks
	Tree pruner
	Staple-less stapler
Foldable helmet	

Table 2: List of Inspiration Cards

Products that were described on the Inspiration Cards were carefully selected based on the two criteria mentioned earlier. The final card contained a photograph of the item and a typical scene of how it could be used in an everyday context accompanied by a short description of how it works (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Examples of Inspiration Cards

Participants went through these photographs first individually, and later in groups. Just like during the Download Session, participants wrote down anything that was interesting or intriguing about these products and discussed them. As the process took time for discussion and decision-making, the facilitator advised focusing on two to three cards. Using the selective cards the participants had been most inspired by and returning to the issues from the Download Session, each of the four teams came up with a product idea and usage scenarios by the end of the session.

SESSION 4: FINAL IDEAS

After generating ideas through the Inspiration Session, each team presented their product ideas and usage scenarios with the rest of the participants and the observers. Each group presented the concept in front of their panels, using the cards and notes they had placed earlier. After describing the issues and solutions they had come up with, each group presented a skit to describe the usage scenarios of their concept (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Describing a product usage scenario using a skit

The following list describes the concept, issues, and product ideas presented by the four groups, respectively:

1. *Circle-kul*. The team came up with this idea as during the download session, a queue and a social tension was found around the public water tap placed in a slum neighborhood of Bangalore. The product is a water container, also serving as a chair, which together with others would create a circle around the water source. The Inspiration Cards they used were: unicycle and kotatsu.
2. *Movie Dustbin*. As the title suggests, this is a public dustbin, which plays a piece of a Bollywood film as one throws a piece of trash inside. The team came up with the idea through Download Cards as they saw trash scattered on the streets. The Inspiration Cards they used were: unicycle and Nintendo DS.
3. *Trust Bank*. An object, which holds a personal work (identity/trust) record in the form of a card or a charm. Inside, users can place a *trust credit*, which they can accumulate through work or service in quality. The idea came from Indian homes which have refrigerators with locks; the team thought it would be important for both service providers for homes and users to have ways to appreciate quality services.
4. *God Bless ID Necklace*. The team came up with a product concept of a necklace, which stores your personal information for people who suffer by living without national identification system. The concept suggested that the necklace should take

the shape of Hindu gods of choice, so that it could also appeal to one's conscience and prevent it from being stolen. The team used several inspiration cards, including mobile phone trinkets for its shape, and NIKE+ for its capability to store personal data.

After each team presented their concept, reviewers who were appointed prior to the workshop, commented on each idea. All four ideas were of a high quality and received positive reviews from observers from both India and Japan.

DISCUSSION

As a case study, we organized a workshop called the 'Innovation Workshop for India', applying this method. There were total of 20 participants divided into four teams, each of which generated some creative ideas within 3.5 hours of workshop time.

The workshop has so far only covered the phase of ideation thus it is too early to conclude whether ideas created from such workshops are 'disruptive' enough. However, we have received positive feedback, particularly from the observers of the workshop. According to one of the VLFM members, the i.school was 'eye-opening': "Participants of the workshop have come up with excellent ideas in half a day, which we would have not come up in 50 or 60 days."

One of the Japanese observers who runs a company in India and is very much aware of the challenges that face Japanese industries, noted the approach is very different from the current convention and thus can be a breakthrough: "A typical approach for Japanese corporations is that they localize existing products and ideas rather than taking the local situations into account. There are in fact very few cases that products and services with new concepts are made for India."

Positive feedback also came from participants. One participant, who works for a domestic electronics company mentioned: "The place enables that without all of us going on a fieldwork, the facts can be shared and turn them into a collective knowledge. It was a precious experience to broaden the perspective and to revisit the strengths that lie in

technologies built into everyday products of one's own country." His opinion showed that even for the practitioners the general workshop provided a high level of satisfaction.

Although we have received much positive feedback, organizers have identified several issues by reviewing the process. In particular, the following describe the issues we have identified from the Download and Inspiration Session, both of which consist of the core part of this method.

IMPROVING THE DOWNLOAD SESSION

From the Download Session, two important improvement areas came up: (1) the limitation of what can be implied through the field of target, and (2) an oversight of multiple meanings in symbols.

The first improvement area is well described in the point that has been made by one of the VLFM members: "Bangalore is not the city with all the prospects of the entire India." Photographs and field notes utilized in this workshop were primarily collected from the city and its neighboring areas. Needless to say, many countries, and more so in India, consist of diverse races, religions, customs, languages, and industries. Although Bangalore represents one of the aspects of India, particularly in its rapid development in IT areas, it hardly covers nor represents the entirety of Indian society and culture. Broadening the scope of ideation to the whole of 'India' may be appropriate as we seek to generate ideas that could impact the society in a wider area; but how can fieldwork correspond to this need?

The second point was also pointed out by a member of the VLFM program, as the download has briefly touched the presence of gods observed in the Indian city. Depending on the locations where the icons were found, the very same god could convey different prayers. Insufficient understanding on such contexts and religions could often lead to an incorrect interpretation upon download. How to interpret symbols inbuilt into a society is an issue that anthropology has been facing for over 100 years. As our effort is to make sure that innovation is

properly rooted and connected to the real world, this issue cannot be an oversight.

Neither of the two areas can easily be overcome. One simple solution to overcome the challenges in the Download Session is, naturally, to allocate a researcher with distinguished knowledge, skills, and experience. However, such a high dependency on particular personnel with a particular attribute implies that this idea-brokering could not become a method of its own. Therefore, what can be an alternative solution?

As Wagner (1975) once pointed out: “The only way in which a researcher could possibly go about the job of creating a relation between such entities would be to simultaneously know both of them, to realize the relative character of his own culture through the concrete formulation of another.” By mentioning this discourse, Wagner assumed a single anthropologist. However, we should not limit ourselves to think that understanding cultures, one of our own and another of the subject, does not have to be accomplished by single personnel. Through collaborative effort with locals who could bring a deep understanding of the society and culture in subject, it maybe possible to gain insights of a high standard that is considered requisite to anthropologists. The solution still has a dependency on the existing skills of the participants, however, which seems to be much more realistic than identifying ‘the one’.

IMPROVING THE INSPIRATION SESSION

In the Inspiration Session, the issue we identified was the concentration on cards used for the ideation. As we mentioned previously, 21 items were chosen to be placed on each Inspiration Card based on two criteria, which were: (1) application to multiple purposes, and (2) the product being generated based on the understanding of the people. When we looked at the cards used during the workshop, we discovered that participants had chosen cards, which fulfilled (1) items with high applicability. To be specific, those cards were the unicycle, kotatsu (the low table with heating system), Nike+, and a mobile phone cleaner.

Could it be that criteria (2) was unsuitable for the Inspiration Cards? According to our opinion, that is not necessarily the case, as the ineffectiveness of these cards might have been due to the way we preceded the Inspiration Session. In the beginning of the session, the facilitator encouraged four teams to choose two to three cards, rather than working with all, due to time constraints. The advice may have led to a situation where teams chose cards that had direct implications on forms and usage, in other words, cards which fulfilled the first criteria, were chosen over the second. As products listed in (2) are based on their sources of inspiration rather than the final product, the innovative elements of these products were implicit and naturally required more thinking and discussions in the process of decision-making. As a result, these cards became more difficult to deal with in such a workshop where there was a limited amount of time. Another issue to revisit is how the cards were described. In order to have consistent layouts between cards, both (1) and (2) cards had similar descriptions which centralized the feature and usage of a product. This, we have concluded, was simply a mistake. One sentence should describe a product, for instance the Nintendo DS could have been described as “a device that focuses on enriching the owner’s everyday life” (Nintendo, 2007), or the Shun-Soku as “a pair of sneakers optimized for beating others in curves” (Tsubata, 2010). For (1) cards are about their application to different purposes, the description should mention such nature; and when it comes to (2) cards, as we intended to inspire participants with their uniqueness and innovation during the development, those stories should have been described rather than the product features. These points should be reflected and improved on as we organize workshops in the future.

EFFECT OF OBSERVERS

As mentioned earlier, there were 10 industry leaders who have been engaged in innovative products and its creation practices in public sectors and industries of India, observing the workshop throughout. The industry leaders’ presence was not expected in the first place, however, it became a great support as participants tried to gain understanding from the Download Session and to evaluate their own ideas

from the Inspiration Session. In case of applying the method to the areas of product development of a specific industry, the presence of advanced users or users with specific needs could have the same effect as having such observers to enhance trust in the workshop process and to gain confidence in idea generation.

CONCLUSION

In today's dynamic corporate environment, organizations and employees are continuously in demand to think out-of-the-box, how existing products or services could improve, or even be targeted other than the existing market. In order to meet this demand, IDEO and other design firms have been providing human-centered innovation processes, and have shown certain progress.

On the other hand, to execute such a process, often requires time and investment: some projects could last for months, or in some cases, years. Often this is not something that an organization could deploy as they keep their business as usual. Methodology on how we could execute human-centered innovation in a concise yet effective manner is highly expected in corporate practice in the field of product development and design.

In order to overcome this problem, we developed a method called the idea-brokering workshop as a practical and concise process of human-centered innovation. In the workshop, a group of people with relatively high homogeneity would gain rich and diverse perspectives and be able to generate new product ideas in a short period of time, a total of 3.5 hours. We applied this method and organized a 'Innovation Workshop for India', where the majority of the participants were Japanese and generated product ideas aimed at India. As a result, many novel ideas were generated and have received positive comments from both Indian and Japanese reviewers. Deficiency in two core sessions, namely the Download and Inspiration Sessions, were identified for future improvement.

Based on these results, there are two areas we must consider revisiting. The first area is the validity of the idea-brokering workshop as a method in case

participants with diverse backgrounds. In particular, we would like to consider whether the method could bring positive effects under the global business environment where members of the group can already be multi-national. Testing the approach within a diverse environment would verify how far this method could be applied. Another area is to challenge the required workshop duration even further. In the case study, a total of 3.5 hours was spent on the workshop; considering the time required in past ideation processes taking a human-centric approach, the Innovation Workshop for India was substantially short; however, we are very much aware that reserving four hours for a workshop for a substantial number of people in a business environment can be difficult. Can, such an approach be taken in less than an hour? If an intense yet short workshop can be executed, the approach can bring a completely new opportunity, as ideation workshops can be organized as part of a daily routine. Surely it would be attractive if innovation could be a part of our everyday routine, just like the way we spend small slots of time for coffee or a morning run?

REFERENCES

- Aguilar, F.J. (1967) *Scanning the Business Environment*. New York, NY: Macmillan.
- Barthes, R. (1977). "Rhetoric of the Image." *Image, Music, Text*. Ed. and trans. Stephen Heath. New York, NY: Hill and Wang, 32-51.
- Barthes, R. (1981) *Camera Lucida: Reflections on Photography*, New York, NY: Hill and Wang.
- Bateson, G., Mead, M. (1942) *Balinese Character: A Photographic Analysis*. New York, NY: The Academy of Sciences.
- Brown, A., Weiner, E. (1985) *Supermanaging: How to Harness Change for Personal and Organizational Success*. New York, NY: Mentor.
- Brown, J., Denning, S., Groh, K., Prusak, L. (2004) *Storytelling in Organizations: Why Storytelling Is Transforming 21st Century Organizations and Management*. Oxford, UK: Butterworth-Heinemann.
- Byers, P. (1964) Still photography in the systematic recording and analysis of behavioral data. *Human Organization*, Vol. 23, No.1, 78-84.
- Christensen, C., Overdorf, M. (2000) Meeting the challenge of Disruptive Change. *Harvard Business Review*, March-April 2010. Boston, Massachusetts: Harvard Business Publishing.
- Coates, V.T., Coates, J.F., Jarratt, J., Heinz, L. (1985) Issues identification and management: The state of the art of methods and techniques. *Research project 2345-28*. Palo Alto, CA: Electric Power Research Group.
- Collier, J. Jr., Collier, M. (1986) *Visual Anthropology: Photography as a Research Method*. Albuquerque, NM: University of New Mexico Press.

- Cramer, M., Sharma, M., Salvador, T., Beauregard, R. (2008) Video utterances: expressing and sustaining ethnographic meaning through the product development process. In: Cefkin, M., Cotton, M. (Eds.), *EPIC2008: In Being Seen: Paradoxes and Practises of Invisibility*, Proceedings of EPIC 2008. Ethnographic Praxis In Industry Conference, October 15-18, Copenhagen, Denmark, 116-127.
- Dalsgaard, A. L. (2008) Verfremdung and business development: the ethnographic essay as eye-opener. In: Cefkin, M., Cotton, M. (Eds.), *EPIC2008: In Being Seen: Paradoxes and Practises of Invisibility*, Proceedings of EPIC 2008. Ethnographic Praxis In Industry Conference, October 15-18, Copenhagen, Denmark, 146-159.
- Faulkner, S. A., Zafiroglu, A. C. (2010) The power of participant-made videos: intimacy and engagement with corporate ethnographic video. In: Luis Arnal, L., Pulman-Jones, S., Tamura, H. (Eds.), *EPIC2010: Dō / The Way of Ethnography*, Proceedings of EPIC 2010. Ethnographic Praxis In Industry Conference, August 29-September 1, Tokyo, Japan, 113-121.
- Gaver, W.W., Dunne, A., Pacenti, E. (1999) Cultural probes. *Interactions*, Vol. 1, No.1, 21-29.
- i.school, the University of Tokyo (2011) *Annual Report 2010*. <http://ischool.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp/news/annualreport2010> (accessed May 16, 2011).
- Ichikawa, K. (1977) *SOZO-KOGAKU (Creative Engineering)*. Tokyo, Japan: LATIS (in Japanese)
- Johnsen, T.E., Helmersen, P. (2008) Contextualizing customers. In: Cefkin, M., Cotton, M. (Eds.), *EPIC2008: In Being Seen: Paradoxes and Practises of Invisibility*, Proceedings of EPIC 2008. Ethnographic Praxis In Industry Conference, October 15-18, Copenhagen, Denmark, 185-196.
- Kelly, T. (2001) *The Art of Innovation*. New York, NY: Crown Business.
- Kim, W. C., Mauborgne, R. (2005) *Blue Ocean Strategy: How to Create Uncontested Market Space and Make Competition Irrelevant*. Boston, Massachusetts: Harvard Business Press.
- Leung, A. K., Maddux, W. W., Galinsky, A. D., Chiu, C. (2008) Multicultural experience enhances creativity: The when and how. *American Psychologist*, Vol.63, No.3, 169-181.
- Nintendo (2007) *Nintendo Annual Report 2007*; <http://www.nintendo.co.jp/ir/pdf/2007/annual0703e.pdf> (accessed May 19, 2011).
- Noguchi, H. (1998) An exploratory study on 'Cross-Inference Model' for supporting idea generation process of industrial design, *Proceedings of KES' 98 (Adelaide)*, Vol. 1, 384-389.
- Page, S.E. (2007) *The Difference: How the Power of Diversity Creates Better Groups, Firms, Schools, and Societies*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press.
- Segelstrom, F., Raijmakers B., Holmlid, S. (2009) Thinking and doing ethnography in service design. In: *Rigor and Relevance in Design*, Proceedings of IASDR 2009. International Association of Societies of Design Research, October 18-22, Seoul, Korea, 4349-4358.
- Surowiecki, J. (2005) *The Wisdom of Crowds*. New York, NY: Anchor.
- Tsubata, Y. (2010) UNDOU-KAI-NO TEITEN-KANSOKU GA UNDA "SHUN-SOKU" NO KAKKI-TEKI CONCEPT (How Continuous Observation of School Athletic Meet Generated A Groundbreaking Concept of "Shun-soku"), Yomiuri Ad-report OJO, October - November 2010 Issue, *Yomiuri Shimbun*, 2010. (in Japanese).
- Verganti, R. (2009). *Design-Driven Innovation*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business Press.
- VLFM (2011) <http://nmcc.nic.in/VLMP.aspx> (accessed May 20, 2011).
- Wagner, R. (1975) *The Invention of Culture - Revised and Expanded Edition*. Chicago, IL: The University of Chicago Press.
- Young, J.W. (2003) *A Technique for Producing Ideas*. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.